

**WOMEN EMPOWERMENT AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN
AKWA IBOM STATE: EVALUATION OF DAKKADA WOMEN
ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND MENTORSHIP PROGRAMME (DWEMP)**

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ABSTRACT

Women empowerment in Nigeria is an economic process that involves empowering Nigerian women as poverty alleviation and illiteracy reduction measure. The Dakaada Women Entrepreneurship and Mentorship programme (DWEMP) is one of the flagships of Governor Udom Emmanuel led Akwa Ibom State Government and it is domiciled in the Directorate of Marketing and Brand Management, Office of the Governor, Akwa Ibom State. The initiative was born out of the driven passion of state's government in its desire to empower women as a strategy for socioeconomic development. This survey research sought to examine the how the Dakaada Women Entrepreneurship and Mentorship programme (DWEMP) has contributed to the empowerment of Akwa Ibom women. The Feminist Theory was adopted for a theoretical framework for the study. To achieve the aim of the study, 3 hypothesis were tested with data collected from field through questionnaire. Chi-square was use to test the hypothesis and findings of the study shown that the Dakkada Women Entrepreneurship and Mentorship Programme (DWEMP) is actually on the course of empowering women across Akwa Ibom State with vocational skill through training and manpower mobilization, that women empowerment has a crucial role to play in the development of Akwa Ibom State, and it is right for women to share in the collective wealth of their society through strategically-planned and executed empowerment programmes. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher among other recommended that Dakkada Women Entrepreneurship and Mentorship Programme (DWEMP) should be encouraged by the coming governments and empowered for sustainable programmes.

KEYWORDS: Women, Women Empowerment, Dakkada Women Entrepreneurship and Development

INTRODUCTION

Women empowerment in Nigeria is an economic process that involves empowering Nigerian women as poverty and illiteracy reduction measure. Empowerment is the development of women in terms of politics, social and economic strength in nation development. It is also a way of reducing women's vulnerability and dependency in all spheres of life. It can be noted that the aggregate of educational, political, health and legal empowerments are key to women's empowerment in Nigeria. Like many African women, Nigerian women play a subordinate role to their male counterparts. There are twice as many women below the poverty line than men, and up to 19 times as many men in executive and legislative positions than women (Akpanim, 2006). At the core of Nigeria's social imbalance is a distorted power dynamic in determining family size as the male-centered focus points to a critical population problem. Women are eliminated from the decision-making process of how many children they are going to have and when they are to have them. There are very few population control guides that target men to reduce high fertility rates. There are imbalances within marriage, religious and government institutions and access to good health programme. The United, as well as a majority of nations across the world have developed and organized programmes which aim to ameliorate gender inequalities. Education has been considered to be a very important aspect of economic growth with women positioned in it for empowerment (Dension, 1992).

Only a handful of women exist on the Nigerian political scene as this was never the case about two decades ago. Male domination of decision making and violence has led to women not feeling free and comfortable enough to engage in political matters. Moreover, successful political advisors are not likely to support female candidates so it will be difficult for them to pave a path in politics. When women in business have fewer employees and shorter longevity than men, this gender gap becomes even wider (Omorode, 2014). There have been some national investments to expand women-led business in Nigeria such as advocating startups and productivity through grants, mentoring and business technical training. The Youth Enterprise with Innovation in Nigeria (YOUWIN) gives insight to young men and women on how to carry out their business ideas and conquer certain challenges that came with starting a business.

In addition, the Nigerian government initiated the Women's Fund for Economic Empowerment and Business Development for women entrepreneurs, while second chance was meant to reintroduce dropout women due to pregnancy, back to school. Data show that the number of senior female civil servants was judged to be 22.5% while judicial appointments across the 36 states constituted about 30% (Okemakinde, 2014). A national policy on Sexual harassment in Educational institutions had been put in place. Free medical treatments were provided for female victims of domestic and sexual violence and temporary shelters were being built nationwide. It has been observed that Nigeria is also working to improve the education of girls by recruiting more female teachers, creating skill acquisition programmes for girls and women as well as providing textbooks at subsidized rates among other measures.

In Nigeria, the effect of women empowerment can be measured using indices such as education, literacy rate, employment and leadership roles. Omorode (2014) stated that high rates of maternal mortality and violence against women make Nigeria one of the toughest places in the world to be born a girl. Educationally, statistics shows that women are not

favoured in the evolution of the educational system in the country with 37.75% of population in primary schools are girls while only 29% of undergraduates were females (Okemakinde, 2014). In absolute terms, there is a ratio of 1:3 females and males in Nigeria tertiary institutions and this is due to the lingering perception of the society on gender inequalities.

The empowerment and mobilization of women into the affairs of governance and business is one of the indices of measuring a developed economy. Nigerian women have encountered large scale marginalization in business, politics and education as women continue to be victims of social stigmatization and relegation from the secular scene. More often than not, men constitute a larger percentage of party membership and thus, sometimes negatively affect women when it comes to selecting party standard bearers and public office holders. The plethora of men on the political scene in Nigeria has resulted to the constitution of women as the minority gender/group and this has led to the marginalization of women off the stages of public affairs. However, Akpanim (2006) believes that low political participation as well as insufficient funding to women empowerment programmes are also other factors that hamper the success of women empowerment programmes in Nigeria. Women, mostly in the north and south are not allowed to participate in politics especially in the capacity of being voted for.

It is good to point out that efforts of women in the development of the society will only be optimally utilized if they are being empowered socially, culturally, politically and economically. Women participation is very crucial in the development drive of developing countries as meeting development goals may not be fully actualized without their full involvement. The situation of women has grown worse by the fact that there are some husbands who may not approve their wives to participate in any social club or economic venture, possibly due to perceived fear of exposure and the threat of being taken over by another man.

In Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, some pockets of women empowerment programmes exist since the advent of democracy in 1999. Women organizations such as Nka Uforo Iban, District Ladies of Iman Ibom, Women of worth, Akwa Ibom Women of Vision, Akwa Ibom Young Ladies Association and the Family Life Enhancement programme initiated by the state's former first lady, Mrs. Unoma God'swiill Akpabio. Also, the Family Empowerment and Youth Re-orientation Path initiative by Her Excellency, Mrs. Martha Udom Emmanuel is one of the leading women empowerment programmes that is focused on empowering rural women by providing houses for widows across the state, reducing maternal and infant mortality, combating HIV/AIDS among women as well as orientating young girls on the need to attain educational skills in order to maintain economic independence.

The Dakkada Women Entrepreneurial and Mentorship Programme (DWEMP) is an initiative of the Directorate of Marketing and Brand Management, Office of the Akwa Ibom State Governor and it is born out of the desire to inspire, reorient of mentor and support Akwa Ibom women in their drives for economic and mental independence. The initiative has a vision to enhance the knowledge and provide opportunities for women to develop and sustain their entrepreneurial skills and connect them to financial opportunities available both in the state and in the country to foster unity and development for a better future for Akwa Ibom women.

DWEMP is designed to share best practices, discuss common challenges facing women of Akwa Ibom State. One of the major prospects of the programme which marks it out

of other previous women empowerment programmes is that, it is aimed in establishing a relationship with at least, one server business mentor, build network with policy makers, companies, and industries, associate with non-profit groups available in the state. With this in mind, there is a high tendency of longevity. It is the wish of DWEMP to align with multilateral development organizations and also form connections with diverse network with Akwa Ibom, Nigerian and African women entrepreneurs. Its effort also has to strengthen strategies, leadership and business management skills in women of Akwa Ibom State. The initiative is principally aimed at ensuring that all Akwa Ibom women gain skills set needed to grow and scale their enterprises. It is also aimed at developing a tool kit of soft skills, including self-confidence, resilience, career goals, relationship languages, collaborations and cross-cultural communications among women within and outside the state.

In Akwa Ibom State, there is inadequate provision of facilities to ensure the socio-economic development of women. In the rural areas of the state, women suffer a myriad of socio-cultural problems like illiteracy, economic dependence, social in-exposure, maternal mortality, female genital mutilation (female circumcision), sex selective education and a host of other gender-based violence. Most families prefer to educate their sons to girls, especially in cases where the family's financial insufficiency demands the educational training of one or few of the children. The daughters are immediately married off to men of which, they function as house wives who emotionally and economically depend on their husbands for virtually all forms of sustenance.

All these hindrances eventually hamper the full female participation in socioeconomic and political activities in the development of the state and Nigeria. Despite the contributions of women to socioeconomic development strategies, they are never treated with dignity and recognition as they should deserve. Women are still seen as second fiddle as many men believe that placing women in the background of society is at their best interests. Women who can strive to attain socioeconomic relevance are still not recognized and respected because of their perceived roles as second-class citizens by their male counterparts. The oppression and marginalization of women in our society has really deprived women of the opportunity to contribute to the development of their own state and country as a whole.

The need for the empowerment and socioeconomic development of women is anchored on the germane reason that they also have a part to play in the development of their society. The Dakkada Women Entrepreneurship and Mentorship Programme (DWEMP) is formulated and driven along the line to correcting the status quo about women in Akwa Ibom State as economic and social dependents. Economic programmes anchored around women have been proven to provide a positive a widespread result of which men and children will be prime beneficiaries.

Women empowerment in Nigeria is relatively very low as the rate of women that have been socially and economically excluded is enormous. In his study, he found that several women empowerment programmes in the country have not actually gotten to the grassroots in order to affect the lives of the common rural woman. Again, the impacts of women empowerment programmes have been highly politicized. Similarly, there exist a huge form of tribalism and ethnicity in the women empowerment programmes in Nigeria. According to them, women empowerment programmes in Nigeria are channeled along ethnic, tribal and religious lines as those who control these empowerments tend to channel the benefits to the

regions which they hail from as this strongly reduces the efficacy of the programmes.

The patriarchal structure of Africa has completely relegated and marginalized the African women to the background of society, thereby placing them in the fetters of ignorance, poverty and dependence. Lack of educational skills, therefore hampers their chances of full maximization of women empowerment programmes in Nigeria (Agba, 2005). One of the fundamental problems of women empowerment programmes in Nigeria is lack of continuity. Many of the beneficiaries of these past and respective women empowerment programmes are not followed-up to ensure success and accountability. Because of the lack of continuum in the Nigerian governmental system, there is no database or records for these beneficiaries. This sadly results to double-entry or complete omission. A database would show the beneficiaries as well as the population of those that are under empowered. There is also the corruption factor in women empowerment programmes in Nigeria (Agba, 2005). These problems therefore heighten the issue surrounding women empowerment programmes in the country. This study therefore is poised to assess the extent to which DWEMP implements their activities in order to indeed empower women in Akwa Ibom State.

HYPOTHESIS

- H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between the impacts of Dakkada Women Entrepreneurship and Mentorship program (DWEMP) and the development of Akwa Ibom Women
- H₀₂:** There is no correlation between socio-economic infrastructures and the socio-economic development of women in Akwa Ibom State.
- H₀₃:** There is no significant association between women empowerment and the socioeconomic development of Akwa Ibom State.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Feminist Theory

The theory adopted for this study is the feminist theory which is centered on the equality of the sexes in socio-economic, political and religious climates. This theory advocates for equal political, social, education, and religious opportunities for women and men. The theory was first coined by a French socialist, Charles Fourier in 1837 and has been used and branded in many academic disciplines in the world. One of the major propositions of feminism is that there exist differences in social roles, experiences, interest and chores between men and women and these differences are socially structured to the advantage of men. The theory is a reaction to the many centuries of marginalization and relegation of women from the secular stage. In reaction to these many centuries of male domination, the feminist theory is aimed at understanding and explaining the intricacies that surround the subject of gender inequality and gender roles, while also trying to explain the blurred line that exist between men and women within a social construct.

The theory was originally designed to address the growing rate of oppression faced by women globally without recourse to tribe, nationality, religion, status and age. Feminist campaigns have recorded some landmark successes in the world, especially in western or developed countries as issue that affect the wellbeing of women, like women's suffrage, freedom to make decisions as it affects reproductive health education, equal employment status and wages as well as freedom to enter into contracts without the approval of their men

have been addressed. The rights for women in society as entrenched in the feminist theory have been advocated by women like Funmilayo Ransome-Kuti and Margaret Ekpo of which, their actions have achieved some appreciable degree of successes. In the application of the theory to the study, the theory justifies the need for female/women empowerment programmes as a panacea to socioeconomic development. Development is never complete without the full and equal participation of women in the affairs of their own country. This theory therefore, mirrors the oppressive practices associated with patriarchy while also seeking increased access to education, healthcare and improved life choices for women through women empowerment programmes.

METHODOLOGY

The survey research design was adopted in this study. The area of the study is Akwa Ibom State. It is made up of 31 local government areas and covers a total land area of 7.081km² with a density of 770/km² (2,000/sq. mi). Akwa Ibom is one of the states in Nigeria and it is located in the coastal southern part of the country. The state is located in the South-South geopolitical zone (Oviasuyi and Uwadiae, 2010). The population of this study is specifically the total number of women in the 17 local government areas that DWEMP has so far covered and that totals 923, 194 (NPC, 2020). The formula developed by Taro Yarmane (1967) for the determination of sample size on a known population was used to determine the sample size of the work. The formula is given as in equation;

$$N/[1+N(e)]^2$$

Where

- N - population size
- n - Sample size
- i - Unity or constant factor
- e - Level of error or significance

In this study, the target population was 985,728 and the level of tolerable error (error margin) is 5% meaning that the researcher is 95% confident that women empowerment programmes in Akwa Ibom State can lead to the socioeconomic development of the state at large. The level of significance (e) is:

$$5/100 = 0.05$$

Using the formula, the researcher had 400 approximately as the sample size.

The sample size of 400 was distributed across the 17 LGAs of which DWEMP has so far covered. The formulated hypotheses were tested using the chi-square (χ^2) test, in order to measure the relationship between women empowerment and the socioeconomic development of Akwa Ibom State. In the Chi-square test, if the calculated value is greater than the critical value at a given level of significance, the null hypothesis (H_0) must be rejected while accepting the alternative hypothesis (H_1) and vice versa. For the purpose of this study, a 95% confidence level was adopted leaving room for only 5% (0.05) tolerable error (level of significance at 0.05).

RESULT

Hypotheses one

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between the activities of DWEMP and the socio-

economic development of women in Akwa Ibom State

	SA	A	D	SD	TOTAL
There is a significant relationship between the activities of DWEMP and the socio-economic development of women in Akwa Ibom State.	184	176	12	18	390
There is no significant relationship between the activities of DWEMP and the socio-economic development of women in Akwa Ibom State	03	02	02	03	10
TOTAL	187	178	14	21	400

Source: Field Survey, 2022

O	E	$o - e$	$(o - e)^2$	$\frac{\sum (o - e)^2}{e}$
184	182.33	1.67	2.79	0.02
176	173.55	2.45	6.00	0.03
12	13.65	-1.65	2.72	0.20
18	20.48	-2.48	6.15	0.30
03	4.68	-1.48	2.19	0.47
02	4.45	-2.45	6.00	1.35
02	0.35	1.65	2.72	7.78
03	0.53	2.47	6.10	11.51
				21.66

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Degree of freedom} &= (\text{No. of Rows} - 1) \times (\text{No. of Columns} - 1) \\
 &= (2 - 1) \times (4 - 1) \\
 &= 1 \times 3 \\
 &= 3 @ 0.05 \text{ level of significance} \\
 &= 7.81
 \end{aligned}$$

Decision: Since the Chi-square (X^2) value (21.66) is greater than the critical value (7.81), H_0 is rejected and H_1 accepted at 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is a significant relationship between the activities of DWEMP and the socio-economic development of women in Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis Two

HO₂: There is no correlation between socio-economic infrastructures and the socio-economic development of women in Akwa Ibom State.

	SA	A	D	SD	TOTAL
There is correlation between socio-economic infrastructures and the socio-economic development of women in Akwa Ibom State.	87	134	62	18	301
There is no correlation between socio-economic infrastructures and the socio-economic development of women in Akwa Ibom State.	27	18	19	35	99
TOTAL	114	152	81	53	400

Source: Field Survey, 2022

O	E	o - e	(o - e) ²	$\frac{\sum (o - e)^2}{e}$
87	85.79	1.21	1.46	0.02
134	114.38	19.62	384.94	3.37
62	60.95	1.05	1.10	0.02
18	39.88	-21.88	478.73	12.03
27	28.22	-1.22	1.49	0.05
18	37.62	-19.62	384.94	10.23
19	20.05	-1.05	1.10	0.05
35	13.12	21.88	478.73	36.49
				62.26

Degree of freedom = (No. of Rows - 1) x (No. of Columns - 1)
 = (2 - 1) x (4 - 1)
 = 1 x 3
 = 3 @ 0.05 level of significance
 = 7.81

Decision: Since the X² value (62.26) is greater than the critical value (7.81), we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. This means that there is a correlation between socio-economic infrastructures and socio-economic development of women in Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis Three

HO₃: There is no significant association between women empowerment and the socio-economic development of Akwa Ibom State.

	SA	A	D	SD	TOTAL
There is a significant association between women empowerment and the socio-economic development of Akwa Ibom State.	122	113	42	19	296
There is no significant association between women empowerment and the socio-economic development of Akwa Ibom State.	10	09	11	74	104
TOTAL	132	122	53	93	400

Source: Field Survey, 2022

O	E	o - e	(o - e) ²	$\frac{\sum (o - e)^2}{e}$
87	85.79	1.21	1.46	0.02
134	114.38	19.62	384.94	3.37
62	60.95	1.05	1.10	0.02
18	39.88	-21.88	478.73	12.03
27	28.22	-1.22	1.49	0.05
18	37.62	-19.62	384.94	10.23
19	20.05	-1.05	1.10	0.05
35	13.12	21.88	478.73	36.49
				62.26

Degree of freedom = (No. of Rows - 1) x (No. of Columns - 1)
 = (2 - 1) x (4 - 1)
 = 1 x 3
 = 3 @ 0.05 level of significance
 = 7.81

Decision: Since the X² value (62.26) is greater than the critical value (7.81), we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. This means that there is a correlation between socio-economic infrastructures and socio-economic development of women in Akwa Ibom State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study was aimed at assessing women empowerment and socio-economic development in Akwa Ibom State and the specific focus was on the activities of Dakkada Women Entrepreneurship and Mentorship Programme (DWEMP). One of the major findings of the study is that, the Dakkada Women Entrepreneurship and Mentorship Programme

(DWEMP) is actually on the course of empowering women across Akwa Ibom State with vocational skill through training and manpower mobilization. The programme has so far, covered seventeen of thirty-one Local Government Areas in the State and has empowered over 800 women so far as at when this study was conducted.

As regards the specific objectives, the study also found that socio-economic infrastructures are relevant in the socio-economic development of women in Akwa Ibom State. This means that women empowerment cannot be fully accomplished without a corresponding availability of socio-economic structures like schools, empowerment programmes and skills acquisition activities. This finding supports the view of Dension (1992) and Aigbokhan (1999) who had respectively found that educational facilities and general human capital development are crucial preconditions that woman empowerment can strive.

Further findings of the study reveal that women empowerment has a crucial role to play in the development of Akwa Ibom State. Women who had benefitted from this empowerment admitted that they could work and earn their income without fully depending on their house heads (husband or children). By this, empowering women has further resulted in wealth creation, job creation and the reduction of dependency burden. This finding supports the view of Uche and Nwnakezi (2007) who opined that empowering women changes the entire face of society for good because it transforms them by bringing alive, their innate potentials in order to advance the development of society. This advancement in turn, helps the entire society; men and children alike.

The study had also found that it is right for women to share in the collective wealth of their society through strategically-planned and executed empowerment programmes. Women are also part of society and as such, should not be technically marginalized. They should be given equal and fair chance to participate in the affairs of their society. This finding justified that women empowerment is necessary in every developmental programme of any country or state. This supports the opinion of Agba (2005) who opined that women empowerment is the expansion of freedom of choice and action as well as increasing the authority of women over their collective resources. By this justification, DWEMP has been driven to fulfill the obligation of women empowerment in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

The study also found that DWEMP, alongside every other women empowerment programme in this state has the major challenge of funding and financial appropriation. Many central and regional governments do not have women empowerment as their point agendum and this makes it difficult for women empowerment programmes to have sufficient and robust funding. DWEMP selects about 50 beneficiaries from each local government area in the state due to insufficient funding. This supports the finding of Akpanim (2006) who observed that poor funding of women empowerment programmes is one of the banes to the under-development of women in Africa. However, this can be ameliorated if the government can begin to prioritize women empowerment programmes in Akwa Ibom State.

CONCLUSION

This study was poised at assessing the activities of Dakkada Women Entrepreneurship and Mentorship Programme (DWEMP) in their women empowerment drive in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The activities of the programme are so far, commendable, aside many other setbacks facing the smooth running of the organization. DWEMP is driven

by the desire to ensure that women have and experience some level of socio-economic development in order to gain relevance among their male counterparts. So far, the programme has empowered about 800 women across the state with vocational skills and crafts and these women are gainfully engaged now, thereby promoting and adding value to their lives.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher make the following recommendations;

1. Dakkada Women Entrepreneurship and Mentorship Programme (DWEMP) should be encouraged by the coming governments and empowered for sustainable programmes.
2. The government should rank women empowerment as one of the top programmes in their administration.
3. Government and corporate organizations, should as a matter of necessity, prioritize the funding of women empowerment programmes for its effective administration.

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